

Brief Report

Evaluating the Prognostic Value of the Triglyceride–Glucose Index in Different Populations: A Critical Analysis

Antonio E. Pontiroli ^{1,*} and Giovanni Luigi Tripepi ⁴

- ¹ Department of Health Sciences, Università Degli Studi di Milano, 20122 Milan, Italy
² Department of Biomedical Sciences for Health, Università Degli Studi di Milano, 20133 Milan, Italy
³ IRCCS MultiMedica, 20138 Milan, Italy; elena.tagliabue@multimedica.it
⁴ Institute of Clinical Physiology of the National Research Council (IFC-CNR), 56124 Reggio Calabria, Italy; graziella.darrigo@cnr.it (G.D.); giovanni.tripepi@ifc.cnr.it (G.L.T.)
⁵ Department of Medicine and Rehabilitation, Policlinico di Monza, 20900 Monza, Italy; stefano.ciardullo@unimib.it (S.C.); gianluca.perseghin@unimib.it (G.P.)
⁶ Department of Medicine and Surgery, University of Milano Bicocca, 20126 Milan, Italy
* Correspondence: antonio.pontiroli@unimi.it (A.E.P.); lucia.lasala@unimi.it or lucia.lasala@multimedica.it (L.L.S.)

Abstract: Background/Objectives: Recent studies have highlighted the Triglyceride–Glucose Index (TYG) as a significant risk factor for mortality and co-morbidities in various populations, including those with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and cardiovascular diseases. However, its prognostic role in obese individuals remains less clear. **Methods:** Utilizing data from an obese cohort of 1359 subjects and from the 1999–2004 cycles of the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) with 15,267 subjects, this study investigates the prognostic value of TYG and blood glucose in relation to age and sex and other factors such as metabolic syndrome, Charlson Comorbidity Index, T2DM and glucose tolerance, in predicting mortality among obese subjects. Over a median follow-up of about 13 years, 11.3% of the obese cohort and 20.6% of the NHANES cohort died. Our findings indicate that while TYG and blood glucose are significantly related to mortality, they offer only modest improvements over models incorporating age, sex, and other risk factors that showed a prognostic power of 76.1% and 86.0% in the respective cohorts. **Conclusions:** These results suggest that while TYG holds potential as a prognostic biomarker, its utility beyond established risk factors requires further validation in clinical settings.

Keywords: mortality; prognosis; obesity; age; sex; triglyceride; glucose; glucose tolerance; metabolic syndrome; Charlson comorbidity index; diabetes (T2DM); triglyceride–glucose-index

Academic Editor: Haifei Shi

Received: 13 February 2025

Revised: 18 March 2025

Accepted: 19 March 2025

Published: 24 March 2025

Citation: Pontiroli, A.E.; La Sala, L.; Tagliabue, E.; D'Arrigo, G.; Ciardullo, S.; Perseghin, G.; Tripepi, G.L. Evaluating the Prognostic Value of the Triglyceride–Glucose Index in Different Populations: A Critical Analysis. *Nutrients* **2025**, *17*, 1124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu17071124>

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Several papers have appeared recently on the role of the Triglyceride–Glucose Index (TYG). Originally introduced as a low-cost surrogate index of insulin resistance [1,2], TYG is a risk factor for mortality and co-morbidities in the general population, in diabetes mellitus (T2DM), and in patients with cardiovascular diseases [2–4]; only in 2024, 630 papers have appeared in PubMed dealing with TYG [5].

Insulin resistance (IR) is a pathophysiological condition distinguished by the diminished effectiveness of insulin in promoting glucose uptake and utilization. The Triglyceride Glucose (TYG) index, derived from fasting triglyceride (TG) and fasting plasma glucose (FPG) levels, has become a surrogate marker of IR. The TYG is calculated using the formula [1,2]:

$$\ln [fasting\ triglycerides\ (mg/dL) \times fasting\ glucoses\ (mg/dL)]/2$$

This allows simultaneous tracking of changes in triglyceride and glucose levels. Several studies have demonstrated that the TYG correlates with the advancement of metabolic disorders. For instance, in a large National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) 1999–2018 cohort of T2DM patients, TYG enhanced the risk of all-cause mortality in patients aged <65 years, but not in older patients [6]. However, a recent study performed in an Iranian cohort of the general population suggested that the impact of TYG on mortality is limited to T2DM subjects [7]. Older studies on the prognostic value of TYG usually did not compare the results obtained with other possible prognostic indexes (the majority) or showed a similar value [8–10].

The role of TYG in obese subjects is less defined; the only available data indicated that TYG was independently associated with harmful cardiovascular events in young and middle-aged obese US populations [11]. Quite recently, it was shown that TYG, just like blood glucose and metabolic syndrome, is associated with the deterioration of glucose tolerance and with all-cause mortality in obesity [12,13].

Especially with TYG, but also with other suggested prognostic factors (be it the metabolic syndrome [14], the Charlson Index [15], Glucose tolerance (GT), or blood glucose levels), one might wonder how these prognostic factors improve the value of classical and universal risk factors, such as age and sex. To be adopted in everyday clinical practice, a candidate prognostic biomarker should provide prognostic information that exceeds what is offered by well-validated and simple risk prediction rules. For instance, current guidelines recommend considering echocardiography to refine cardiovascular (CV) risk assessment in hypertensive patients, and the measurement of left ventricular mass index (LVMI) is considered an important independent risk factor for mortality and heart failure [16]. However, LVMI did not meaningfully improve risk prediction for these two conditions when added to clinical models [17,18].

The aim of our study was to analyze, in obese subjects [13], the additive role of these prognostic factors (TYG and blood glucose) over more classical and universal risk factors such as age and female sex, plus one of the additional risk factors [metabolic syndrome, T2DM, the Charlson Comorbidity Index, GT, arterial hypertension (AH), and coronary heart disease (CHD)]. To reduce the possible drawbacks of an analysis based on a single cohort, we chose to analyze some of the data in the general population (data obtained from the 1999–2004 cycles of the NHANES [19]) and in a subgroup of obese subjects from the same cohort.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Cohorts in the Study

The first cohort includes obese patients receiving routine medical treatment [13]; subjects undergoing bariatric surgery (BS) were excluded from the study since BS can reduce mortality [20,21]. Therefore, we analyzed a cohort of 1,359 obese subjects (371 men and 988 women, aged 44.1 ± 12.6 years, with a body mass index (BMI) of 39.9 ± 5.2 kg/m², followed by a median period of 13.9 years). The second study cohort includes subjects from the 1999–2004 cycles of the NHANES, [19]; it is made of 15,267 subjects (7389 men and 7878 women, aged 47.1 ± 19.7 years, with a BMI of 28.4 ± 6.5 kg/m², followed for a median period of 13.3 years). A sub-cohort of the same cohort [19] with BMI > 30 kg/m² was also evaluated. In both cohorts, blood glucose and TYG were expressed as quartiles of distribution (blood glucose quartiles (BGQ) and TYG quartiles (TYGQ), respectively). This study represents a second analysis of studies approved by Ethics Committees. The first study protocol [13] was approved by local Ethics Committees in 2015 (Coordinating Center: Ospedale San Paolo, Comitato Etico Interaziendale di Milano Area A, official approval SC: 2015 ST 125), and written informed consent was obtained from all adult participants. The second study protocol [19] was originally approved by the Centers for Disease Control and

Prevention Research Ethics Review Board, and written informed consent was obtained from all adult participants. The present analysis was deemed exempt by the Institutional Review Board at our institutions, as the dataset used in the analysis was completely re-identified.

2.2. Methods and Procedures

Clinical and laboratory characteristics of subjects of the two cohorts under study are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Details of the subjects in the two cohorts. Mean \pm SD.

Obese Cohort [13]		General Population Cohort [19]	
Number (sex M/F) (% men)	1359 (371/988) (27.3%)	Number (sex M/F) (% men)	15,267 (7389/7878) (48.4%)
Age (years)	44.1 \pm 12.6	Age (years)	47.1 \pm 19.7
Body mass index (BMI, kg/m ²)	39.9 \pm 5.2	Body mass index (BMI, kg/m ²)	28.4 \pm 6.5
Median duration of follow-up (years)	13.9	Median duration of follow-up (years)	13.3
BG (mg/dL)	118.1 \pm 47.2	BG (mg/dL)	105.4 \pm 35.5
TYG *	8.9 \pm 0.7	TYG *	8.7 \pm 0.7
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	212.8 \pm 66.4	Cholesterol (mg/dL)	196.8 \pm 43.2
HDL-cholesterol (mg/dL)	50.0 \pm 13.6	HDL-cholesterol (mg/dL)	53.4 \pm 15.9
LDL-cholesterol (mg/dL)	136.5 \pm 64.3	LDL-cholesterol (mg/dL)	117.6 \pm 36.2
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	159.5 \pm 133.2	Triglycerides (mg/dL)	140.7 \pm 121.2
AST (U/L)	25.9 \pm 13.8	AST (U/L)	25.6 \pm 0.2
ALT(U/L)	35.2 \pm 24.0	ALT(U/L)	28.9 \pm 0.4
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.8 \pm 0.2	Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.9 \pm 0.42
Arterial hypertension (%)	425 (31.3%)	Arterial hypertension (%)	5487 (35.9%)
Type 2 diabetes (%)	131 (9.6%)	Type 2 diabetes (%)	1863 (12.2%)
Metabolic syndrome (%)	717 (52.8%)	Metabolic syndrome (%)	4990 (35.1%)
Cardiovascular disease (%)	51 (3.8%)	Cardiovascular disease (%)	1130 (9.3%)
All-cause mortality (sex M/F) (%)	154 (59/95) (11.3%)	All-cause mortality (sex M/F) (%)	3136 (1737/1399) (20.6%)

BG = blood glucose; TYG = triglyceride–glucose-index; ALT = alanine transaminase; AST = aspartate transaminase; * TYG = \ln [triglycerides (mg/dL) \times blood glucose (mg/dL)/2].

2.3. Statistical Analysis

In obese patients of Cohort 1, the prognostic value for mortality BGQ and TYGQ was investigated in analyses of increasing complexity, starting with a basic model, including age and sex, and one of the classical risk factors at a time (T2DM, Charlson Comorbidity Index, Metabolic Syndrome, GT, AH, and CHD). In Cox analyses, data were expressed as the hazard ratio (HI), 95% confidence interval (CI), and *p*-value. The predictive accuracy of each prognostic model was assessed by calculating the Harrell C-index, ranging from 50% to 100%. A Harrell's C index of 50% indicates no discrimination ability of the model being tested, whereas a Harrell's C of 100% indicates perfect discrimination [22]. Some models were analyzed also in the general population. Data analysis was performed by STATA 17 (Stata Corporation, College Station, TX, USA) for MacIntosh.

3. Results

The two cohorts were not intended for direct comparisons and differed in size, sex ratio, BMI, and frequency of cardiovascular diseases; other subtle differences were observed in the frequency of diabetes, metabolic syndrome, and overall mortality, despite similar durations of follow-up and similar frequencies of other medical and metabolic conditions.

Over a median follow-up of 13.9 years, 154 out of 1359 obese subjects of Cohort 1 died (11.3%); over a median follow-up of 13.3 years, 3136 out of 15,267 subjects of Cohort 2 died (20.6%). In cohort 1, a statistical model, including age, sex, and T2DM (Table 2—Basic model), provided a 76.1% prognostic power for predicting mortality. In this model, age, female sex, and T2DM were found to be significantly related to death (always $p < 0.001$). In cohort 2, a statistical model, including age, sex, and T2DM (basic model), provided an 86.0% prognostic power for predicting mortality. In this model, both age, female sex, and T2DM were found to be significantly related to death (always $p < 0.001$). In either cohort, the inclusion of BGQ (Model 1) or TYGQ (Model 2), or both (Model 3), into Model 1 did not materially increase the prognostic power of the same model (HC index ranging from 76.1% to 76.4%, and from 86.0% to 86.1%). Supplementary Table S1 reports the prognostic value of risk factors at univariable Cox regression analyses. This analysis revealed that all risk factors resulted in being significantly related to mortality with a discriminator power (Harrell’C index) ranging from 56.2% to 73.7%.

Table 2. Cox regression analysis and Harrell’C index.

A. Obese Cohort.				
	Basic Model	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Variables (Units of Increase)	HR (95% C.I.), p Value			
Age (years)	1.078 (1.060–1.096), $p < 0.001$	1.075 (1.057–1.094), $p < 0.001$	1.077 (1.059–1.095), $p < 0.001$	1.076 (1.058–1.094), $p < 0.001$
Sex (females versus males)	0.535 (0.386–0.744), $p < 0.001$	0.539 (0.388–0.749), $p < 0.001$	0.561 (0.403–0.781), $p = 0.001$	0.560 (0.402–0.779), $p = 0.001$
Diabetes	1.817 (1.314–2.512), $p < 0.001$	1.341 (0.802–2.244), $p = 0.264$	1.473 (1.009–2.150), $p = 0.045$	1.259 (0.747–2.124), $p = 0.387$
BGQ		1.213 (0.935–1.574), $p = 0.146$		1.126 (0.855–1.483), $p = 0.398$
TYGQ			1.210 (1.006–1.456), $p = 0.043$	1.176 (0.967–1.430), $p = 0.103$
Harrell’C index	76.1%	76.3%	76.3%	76.4%
B. General Population Cohort.				
	Basic Model	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Variables (Units of Increase)	HR (95% C.I.), p-Value	HR (95% C.I.), p-Value	HR (95% C.I.), p-Value	HR (95% C.I.), p-Value
Age (years)	1.094 (1.091–1.097), $p < 0.001$			
Sex (females versus males)	0.662 (0.617–0.711), $p < 0.001$	0.661 (0.615–0.709), $p < 0.001$	0.663 (0.617–0.711), $p < 0.001$	0.661 (0.615–0.710), $p < 0.001$
Diabetes	1.487 (1.371–1.612), $p < 0.001$	1.505 (1.377–1.645), $p < 0.001$	1.501 (1.379–1.633), $p < 0.001$	1.510 (1.381–1.652), $p < 0.001$
BGQ		0.988 (0.952–1.025), $p = 0.528$		0.992 (0.954–1.032), $p = 0.689$
TYGQ			0.985 (0.947–1.024), $p = 0.447$	0.988 (0.948–1.029), $p = 0.560$
Harrell’C index	86.0%	86.0%	86.0%	86.1%

BGQ = blood glucose quartiles; TYGQ = triglyceride-glucose-index Quartiles.

Supplementary Table S2 reports the prognostic value of other risk factors for cohort 1 (A = GT-based model; B = metabolic syndrome-based model; C = AH-based model; D = CHD-based model; E = Charlson Comorbidity index-based model; F = BG based models) and for cohort 2 (G = diabetes analysis restricted to subjects with BMI > 30 kg/m²). In all models and in either cohort, the inclusion of BGQ (Model 1), TYGQ (Model 2), or both (Model 3) into the Basic Model did not meaningfully increase the prognostic power of the same model, the maximum increase being 1.32% (HC index ranging from 76.3% to 76.6%, and from 83.6% to 83.7%, respectively). When BG was entered instead of BGQ, and TYG instead of TYGQ, the significance of the models did never change. In synthesis, the predictive power of TYG did not significantly improve over traditional models.

4. Discussion

In this study, in a large cohort of obese patients (cohort 1) and in an even larger cohort of the general population (cohort 2), multivariable models of various complexities showed that BGQ and TYGQ did not meaningfully improve risk prediction of mortality when added to a prediction model that included only age, sex, and other classical risk factors.

Two recent meta-analyses revealed significant associations between TYG and various health outcomes, suggesting that TYG is a promising biomarker for screening and predicting various medical conditions [23,24]. However, the heterogeneity and methodological quality of the included studies suggest the need for further high-quality research to confirm these findings and refine the clinical utility of the TYG [20,21]. Only a few studies explored the value of TYG in obesity [11–13,25,26], but no one has analyzed the additive role of TYG beyond more classical and universal risk factors such as age and female sex, metabolic syndrome, the Charlson Comorbidity Index, diabetes, glucose tolerance, and blood glucose levels.

In this study, initial univariable Cox regression analyses indicated that all risk factors were significantly related to mortality, with Harrell's C-index values ranging from 53% to 74%, indicating varying levels of discriminatory power. We found that in obese patients and in the general population, age and sex, diabetes, glucose tolerance, metabolic syndrome, the Charlson Comorbidity Index, arterial hypertension, or CHD are significant prognostic factors for mortality. However, while age and sex are coherently significant risk factors, other risk factors show a significant prognostic value when introduced alone, and their effect reduces or vanishes (cohort 1), or is unaffected (cohort 2) when introduced in the model together with BGQ or TYGQ. For cohort 1, similar aspects were found for diabetes, glucose tolerance, metabolic syndrome, the Charlson Comorbidity Index, arterial hypertension, or CHD; for cohort 2, similar aspects were found when the sample of subjects was reduced to subjects with BMI > 30 kg/m². Even though BGQ and TYGQ were significant risk factors when introduced alone, neither BGQ nor TYGQ were of significant value when introduced with other risk factors, either individually or together. Of note, even when statistically significant, the additive role of TYGQ or BGQ was of very limited value, with a maximum percentage increase in the Harrell index of around 1.3%, meaning that none of the factors investigated materially increase the prognostic value of basic models. Of note, a recently published paper [27] investigated the predictive value of adding TYG to Cox regression models, including traditional risk factors, and found that the increase in Harrell's C index was 0.008, which is not different from our data of 0.012. Reasons why neither TYGQ nor BGQ were of significant value as predictors of mortality when added to other traditional risk factors are a matter of speculation. For instance, even though TYG is intuitively more complex than BGQ because of the contemporaneous evaluation of blood glucose and triglycerides, their contribution to other metabolic risk factors like diabetes, glucose tolerance, and metabolic syndrome, is likely to be an overvaluation of aspects already present in the same conditions. A similar possibility applies to the Charlson

Comorbidity Index, which is built on the number of diseases of the individual patient. In addition, since TYG was originally introduced as a low-cost surrogate index of insulin resistance [1,2], similar considerations can apply to arterial hypertension, which is generally characterized by insulin resistance [28,29]. A better prognostic index might be represented by TYG-derived indexes, such as TYG-BMI, TYG-waist circumference, TYG-height, or TYG-waist-hip ratio, which were not analyzed in this study and appear to be more complete indexes [8–10,30–37].

This suggests that while various health and biochemical parameters are individually associated with mortality, age, and sex are the most robust predictors in this cohort. Furthermore, this study, for the first time, demonstrates that although TYG and blood glucose were significantly related to survival in obese patients (i.e., the corresponding hazard ratios are statistically significant), the same biomarkers were not useful for prognostic purposes. This is because the hazard ratio is an index well suited to etiological research but does not, per se, provide information on the prognostic accuracy of a given exposure [38]. Thus, while blood glucose and TYG remain fundamental treatment targets in obese patients, measuring these two factors solely for risk stratification is not justifiable in this condition. In conclusion, other studies are required to state if TYG, as well as blood glucose, can be used as prognostic indexes for mortality in obese subjects and in the general population. The present findings suggest that both TYG and blood glucose, if any, have a very limited role.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/nu17071124/s1>, Table S1: Prognostic value of individual factors at Cox proportional analysis in studies in obese subjects. HR, *p* value, and Harrell's C Index are shown for each factor; Table S2: Cox regression models.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, A.E.P., L.L.S., G.D., S.C., G.P. and G.L.T.; methodology, S.C. and E.T.; formal analysis, A.E.P. and E.T.; investigation, A.E.P. and G.P.; writing—original draft preparation, A.E.P.; writing—review and editing, A.E.P., L.L.S., E.T., G.D., S.C., G.P. and G.L.T. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was funded by Ricerca Corrente of the Italian Ministry of Health to IRCCS MultiMedica, and “The APC was funded by the IRCCS MultiMedica”.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable, see under Section 2.

Data Availability Statement: The research data will be available on request to the authors. The ZENODO platform is used for publicly archived datasets.

Acknowledgments: The authors wish to thank Fondazione Romeo ed Enrica Invernizzi (Milan, Italy) for its support.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest. The authors have no conflict of interest with the content of this paper.

References

1. Khan, S.H.; Sobia, F.; Niazi, N.K.; Manzoor, S.M.; Fazal, N.; Ahmad, F. Metabolic clustering of risk factors: Evaluation of triglyceride-glucose index (TyG index) for evaluation of insulin resistance. *Diabetol. Metab. Syndr.* **2018**, *10*, 74. [PubMed]
2. Hong, S.; Han, K.; Park, C.Y. The triglyceride glucose index is a simple and low-cost marker associated with atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease: A population-based study. *BMC Med.* **2020**, *18*, 361. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
3. Alizargar, J.; Bai, C.H.; Hsieh, N.C.; Wu, S.V. Use of the triglyceride-glucose index (TyG) in cardiovascular disease patients. *Cardiovasc. Diabetol.* **2020**, *19*, 8.
4. Lopez-Jaramillo, P.; Gomez-Arbelaiz, D.; Martinez-Bello, D.; Abat, M.E.M.; Alhabib, K.F.; Avezum, Á.; Barbarash, O.; Chifamba, J.; Diaz, M.L.; Gulec, S.; et al. Association of the triglyceride glucose index as a measure of insulin resistance with mortality and

- cardiovascular disease in populations from five continents (PURE study): A prospective cohort study. *Lancet Healthy Longev.* **2023**, *4*, e23–e33.
5. Available online: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=triglyceride-glucose-index+and+2024> (accessed on 22 November 2024).
 6. Yao, Y.; Wang, B.; Geng, T.; Chen, J.; Chen, W.; Li, L. The association between TyG and all-cause/non-cardiovascular mortality in general patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus is modified by age: Results from the cohort study of NHANES 1999-2018. *Cardiovasc. Diabetol.* **2024**, *23*, 43.
 7. Alavi Tabatabaei, G.; Mohammadifard, N.; Rafiee, H.; Nouri, F.; Maghami Mehr, A.; Najafian, J.; Sadeghi, M.; Boshtam, M.; Roohafza, H.; Haghghatdoost, F.; et al. Association of the triglyceride glucose index with all-cause and cardiovascular mortality in a general population of Iranian adults. *Cardiovasc. Diabetol.* **2024**, *23*, 66.
 8. Yin, H.; Huang, W.; Yang, B. Association between METS-IR index and obstructive sleep apnea: Evidence from NHANES. *Sci. Rep.* **2025**, *15*, 6654. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
 9. Ouyang, Q.; Xu, L.; Yu, M. Associations of triglyceride glucose-body mass index with short-term mortality in critically ill patients with ischemic stroke. *Cardiovasc. Diabetol.* **2025**, *24*, 91.
 10. Zhang, P.; Mo, D.; Zeng, W.; Dai, H. Association between triglyceride-glucose related indices and all-cause and cardiovascular mortality among the population with cardiovascular-kidney-metabolic syndrome stage 0-3: A cohort study. *Cardiovasc. Diabetol.* **2025**, *24*, 92.
 11. Chen, W.; Ding, S.; Tu, J.; Xiao, G.; Chen, K.; Zhang, Y.; Huang, R.; Liao, Y. Association between the insulin resistance marker TyG index and subsequent adverse long-term cardiovascular events in young and middle-aged US adults based on obesity status. *Lipids Health Dis.* **2023**, *22*, 65.
 12. Folli, F.; Pontiroli, A.E.; Zakaria, A.S.; Centofanti, L.; Tagliabue, E.; La Sala, L. Alanine transferase levels (ALT) and triglyceride-glucose index are risk factors for type 2 diabetes mellitus in obese patients. *Acta Diabetol.* **2024**, *61*, 435–440. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
 13. Pontiroli, A.E.; Centofanti, L.; Zakaria, A.S.; Cerutti, S.; Dei Cas, M.; Paroni, R.; La Sala, L.; Tagliabue, E.; Magnani, S.; Folli, F. The triglyceride-glucose index, blood glucose levels, and metabolic syndrome are associated with all-cause mortality in obesity. *Diabetes Metab. Syndr.* **2024**, *18*, 103146. [[CrossRef](#)]
 14. Grundy, S.M.; Brewer, H.B., Jr.; Cleeman, J.I.; Smith, S.C., Jr.; Lenfant, C.; American Heart Association; National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute. Definition of metabolic syndrome: Report of the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute/American Heart Association conference on scientific issues related to definition. *Circulation* **2004**, *109*, 433–438. [[CrossRef](#)]
 15. Charlson, M.E.; Pompei, P.; Ales, K.L.; MacKenzie, C.R. A new method of classifying prognostic comorbidity in longitudinal studies: Development and validation. *J. Chronic Dis.* **1987**, *40*, 373–383. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
 16. Bo, M. Practice guidelines for the management of arterial hypertension of the European Society of Hypertension (ESH) and the European Society of Cardiology (ESC): ESH/ESC task force for the management of arterial hypertension. *J. Hypertens.* **2013**, *31*, 1925–1938.
 17. Tripepi, G.; Pannier, B.; D'Arrigo, G.; Mallamaci, F.; Zoccali, C.; London, G. Reappraisal in two European cohorts of the prognostic power of left ventricular mass index in chronic kidney failure. *Kidney Int.* **2017**, *91*, 704–710. [[CrossRef](#)]
 18. Tripepi, G.; D'Arrigo, G.; Mallamaci, F.; London, G.; Tangri, N.; Hsu, J.Y.; Feldman, H.I.; Zoccali, C. Prognostic values of left ventricular mass index in chronic kidney disease patients. *Nephrol. Dial. Transplant.* **2021**, *36*, 665–672. [[CrossRef](#)]
 19. Ciardullo, S.; Rea, F.; Perseghin, G. Glycated albumin is associated with all-cause and cardiovascular mortality among U.S. adults with and without diabetes: A retrospective cohort study. *Nutr. Metab. Cardiovasc. Dis.* **2022**, *32*, 2375–2382. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
 20. Pontiroli, A.E.; Morabito, A. Long-term prevention of mortality in morbid obesity through bariatric surgery. a systematic review and meta-analysis of trials performed with gastric banding and gastric bypass. *Ann. Surg.* **2011**, *253*, 484–487. [[CrossRef](#)]
 21. Pontiroli, A.E.; Ceriani, V.; Tagliabue, E.; Zakaria, A.S.; Veronelli, A.; Folli, F.; Zononi, I. Bariatric surgery, compared to medical treatment, reduces morbidity at all ages but does not reduce mortality in patients aged < 43 years, especially if diabetes mellitus is present: A post hoc analysis of two retrospective cohort studies. *Acta Diabetol.* **2020**, *57*, 323–333.
 22. Harrell, F.E., Jr.; Califf, R.M.; Pryor, D.B.; Lee, K.L.; Rosati, R.A. Evaluating the yield of medical tests. *JAMA* **1982**, *247*, 2543–2546. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
 23. Nayak, S.S.; Kuriyakose, D.; Polisetty, L.D.; Patil, A.A.; Ameen, D.; Bonu, R.; Shetty, S.P.; Biswas, P.; Ulrich, M.T.; Letafatkar, N.; et al. Diagnostic and prognostic value of triglyceride glucose index: A comprehensive evaluation of meta-analysis. *Cardiovasc. Diabetol.* **2024**, *23*, 310. [[CrossRef](#)]
 24. Sun, Y.; Ji, H.; Sun, W.; An, X.; Lian, F. Triglyceride glucose (TyG) index: A promising biomarker for diagnosis and treatment of different diseases. *Eur. J. Intern. Med.* **2025**, *131*, 3–14. [[PubMed](#)]
 25. Du, L.; Xu, X.; Wu, Y.; Yao, H. Association between the triglyceride glucose index and cardiovascular mortality in obese population. *Nutr. Metab. Cardiovasc. Dis.* **2024**, *34*, 107–111. [[PubMed](#)]
 26. Dang, K.; Wang, X.; Hu, J.; Zhang, Y.; Cheng, L.; Qi, X.; Liu, L.; Ming, Z.; Tao, X.; Li, Y. The association between triglyceride-glucose index and its combination with obesity indicators and cardiovascular disease: NHANES 2003-2018. *Cardiovasc. Diabetol.* **2024**, *23*, 8.

27. Blicher, M.K.; Frary, C.; Pareek, M.; Stidsen, J.V.; Vishram-Nielsen, J.K.K.; Rasmussen, S.; Bonnema, S.J.; Højlund, K.; Olsen, M.H.; Olesen, T.B. Triglyceride-glucose index improves risk prediction beyond traditional risk factors and hypertension mediated organ damage in healthy adults. *Nutr. Metab. Cardiovasc. Dis.* **2024**, *34*, 2446–2454.
28. Velloso, L.A.; Folli, F.; Sun, X.J.; White, M.F.; Saad, M.J.; Kahn, C.R. Cross-talk between the insulin and angiotensin signaling systems. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **1996**, *93*, 12490–12495.
29. Ferrannini, E. A Journey in Diabetes: From Clinical Physiology to Novel Therapeutics: The 2020 Banting Medal for Scientific Achievement Lecture. *Diabetes* **2021**, *70*, 338–346.
30. Wang, X.; Liu, J.; Yu, K.; Huang, Z.; Liu, H.; Li, X. Association between TyG-related parameters and NAFLD risk in Japanese non-obese population. *Sci. Rep.* **2025**, *15*, 7119.
31. Ding, Y.; Li, F.; Zhu, J.; Jiao, X.; Liu, Z.; Liao, Y.; Tao, Q.; Hu, L.; Xiong, S.; Zhai, Z. Prognostic Value of Triglyceride-Glucose Index in Acute Myeloid Leukemia: A Retrospective Study. *Blood* **2024**, *144* (Suppl. S1), 6151. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Chen, Y.; Zhong, Z.; Gue, Y.; Banach, M.; McDowell, G.; Mikhailidis, D.P.; Toth, P.P.; Penson, P.E.; Tomasik, T.; Windak, A.; et al. Impact of surrogates for insulin resistance on mortality and life expectancy in primary care: A nationwide cross-sectional study with registry linkage (LIPIDOGRAM2015). *Lancet Reg. Health Eur.* **2025**, *50*, 101245. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
33. Dui, X.; Chen, X.; Zhu, L.; Han, X.; Ma, T.; Lv, L.; Huang, G.; Hu, L.; Xiao, J.; Dij, Z.; et al. The association between derived TyG index and the risk of heart failure in the elderly population: A prospective cohort study from 2017 to 2023. *BMC Public Health* **2025**, *25*, 863. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
34. Mijangos-Trejo, A.; Gómez-Mendoza, R.; Ramos-Ostos, M.H.; Castro-Narro, G.; Uribe, M.; Juárez-Hernández, E.; López-Méndez, I. Diagnostic Accuracy of the Triglyceride-Glucose Index (TyG), TyG Body Mass Index, and TyG Waist Circumference Index for Liver Steatosis Detection. *Diagnostics* **2024**, *14*, 762. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Pan, L.; Gao, Y.; Han, J.; Li, L.; Wang, M.; Peng, H.; Liao, J.; Wan, H.; Xiang, G.; Han, Y. Comparison of longitudinal changes in four surrogate insulin resistance indexes for incident T2DM in middle-aged and elderly Chinese. *Front. Public Health* **2022**, *10*, 1046223. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Xuan, W.; Liu, D.; Zhong, J.; Luo, H.; Zhang, X. Impacts of Triglyceride Glucose-Waist to Height Ratio on Diabetes Incidence: A Secondary Analysis of a Population-Based Longitudinal Data. *Front. Endocrinol.* **2022**, *13*, 949831. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
37. Xing, Y.; Liu, J.; Gao, Y.; Zhu, Y.; Zhang, Y.; Ma, H. Stronger Associations of TyG Index with Diabetes Than TyG-Obesity-Related Parameters: More Pronounced in Young, Middle-Aged, and Women. *Diabetes Metab. Syndr. Obes.* **2023**, *16*, 3795–3805. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. D'Arrigo, G.; El Hafeez, S.A.; Mezzatesta, S.; Abelardo, D.; Provenzano, F.P.; Vilasi, A.; Torino, C.; Tripepi, G. Common mistakes in biostatistics. *Clin. Kidney J.* **2024**, *17*, sfae197. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.